
SOCIAL MEDIA AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING LECTURER-STUDENT COMMUNICATION AFTER COVID-19

Dr. Chinedu Ifeanyi Okonkwo

Department of Mass Communication Faculty of Social Science, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19882345>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>This study was conducted to x-ray the possibility of adapting social media for lecturerstudent communication in a post-covid-19 era in Nigeria. The researchers anchored this study on the Technological Acceptance Model. This study adopted the online survey method. At the end of the data collection, students and lecturers of twelve (12) tertiary institutions in the country participated in the study; however, there were more students (85%) in the sampled population than lecturers (15%). The study established statistically using the chi-square test of independence that at a significant level of 0.05, students and lecturers of the sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions significantly used social media platforms for lecturers-students' communication, with WhatsApp ranking the most used platform; also, social media platforms were significantly easy to use and valuable for lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions. However, the use of social media significantly affected lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions in a negative way by creating room for familiarity, which had tendencies to breed contempt. The researchers recommended that lecturers and students be cautious and polite when communicating using social media platforms. Students, most significantly, were employed not to misplace the use of social media in communication for informality.</p>	<p>social media, communication, lecturer, student, Covid-19, tertiary</p>

INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of information and communication technology (ICT) has resulted in a rise in the volume and smoothness with which course materials are transferred, thus encouraging the growth of Digital Learning Communities (DLCs) (Ansari & Khan, 2020). Numerous studies have revealed that higher education students are increasingly accepting mobile computing devices like smartphones, tablets, and cell phones in tertiary institutions. According to the Educause Center for Applied Research [ECAR] (2012), roughly 67 percent of surveyed students accepted that mobile devices and social media play a vital role in their academic performance and career enhancement. Students have fantastic educational e-learning

chances because of mobile devices and social media (Gikas & Grant, 2013). Despite the physical distance, academic cooperation, access to course materials and instructors are all possible using mobile devices and social media platforms.

Then, as electronic communication technologies quickly intrude on every aspect of life, educational institutions have struggled for years to comprehend how these tools work to distribute information, make things more useful, and create interactive experiences. (Ansari & Khan, 2020). Adoption and use of mobile devices and social media may give students a plethora of futuristic learning options, including access to course information and engagement with peers and professionals (Nihalani & Mayrath, 2010, Ansari & Khan, 2020). According to the Pew Research Center, 55 percent of American teenagers in the 15 to 17-year-old age group use online social networking sites such as Myspace and Facebook (Reuben, 2008). Reuben claim is relationally tandem with Oji (2011). Oji (2011) citing Okoye (2004) noted the case of information rich and information poor as the level of education and economic stability in countries can help in the adaptation of technological innovation noted the level of education and economic stability help in the adaptation of technological innovation.

In general, it is a common belief by students that social media and mobile devices are the most costeffective and convenient ways to get pertinent information. According to studies conducted in Western nations, using online social media for collaborative learning dramatically impacts students' academic performance and happiness (Zhu, 2012). This study aimed to see how integrating and using mobile devices in sharing resource materials, interacting with colleagues, and students' academic performance influenced learning and teaching activities at higher education institutions. The study's overall purpose was to bring up-to-date students' and lecturers' opinions on using social media for communication after the upsurge of these platforms for education during the COVID-19 lockdown.

Furthermore, this study focused solely on students' and lecturers' experiences with social media and their understanding of how social media affect communication. This study's main research question was: how do students and lecturers perceive the use of social media as they are integrated into higher education for accessing, connecting, and communicating with lecturers or students, respectively?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine how the use of social media can help adapt to lecturer-student communication in a post-COVID-19 in Nigeria. Other objectives of this study are to:

- i. find out the extent to which social media is used for lecturers-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- ii. ascertain the social media platform mostly used for lecturer-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- iii. Determine various ways in which the use of social media has affected lecturer-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the execution of this study:

- i. Social media platforms are not significantly used for lecturers-student communication in Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between social media usage and lecturer-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.
- iii. Social media usage has no significant effect on lecturer-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Lecturer-student communication and relationship in tertiary institutions

Research on motivation and classroom practice typically points to the quality of teacher-student (or lecturer-student) relationships as a critical factor. Positive interactions between students and their lecturers increase the likelihood that they will learn and participate in less disruptive behaviours. Rimm-Kaufman (2015) asserts that strengthening student-teacher relationships has substantial, advantageous, and long-term repercussions for children's academic and social development. Academic progress will not come from strengthening students' relationships with their instructors. The opposite is true: students with close, positive, and encouraging relationships with their teachers will perform better than those who interact less amicably.

In addition, there was a good rapport between teachers and students, which boosted learning and improved academic performance (Schonert-Reichl, 2017). Parents and students both maintained respect for one another and other cultural standards because of the dedication of the teachers. Children look up to their teachers as role models and as a means of advancing in society. The amount of academic support and drilling instructors give their students to ensure success in all spheres is decreasing for various reasons. Numerous goals, aspirations, feelings, and behavioural expectations are expressed between teachers and students, and these exchanges affect the caliber of the bonds they forge and the meaning of their experiences in the classroom. According to Alexander (2022) this account for the reason educational and government authorities in the UK believe that a dearth of role models would be to blame for the issue with boys' disengagement and underperformance in school. Thus, lack or ethnic minority (B.E.M.) teachers are sought for in political mentors' discourses to change the behavior of B.E.M. adolescents without placing any responsibility for the institutionalised racism they encounter in their schools and larger society.

Usage of social media for collaborative learning in tertiary institutions

The phenomena of social media arose in 2005, following the implementation of Web2.0, and is more specifically described as a set of Internet-based apps that build on the conceptual and technological basis of web 2.0 and enable the production and sharing of user-generated content (Oji & Bebenimibo, 2021; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Students' creation, modification, and sharing of text, video, and audio course materials are possible with social media and mobile technology. Developing a new form of learning culture based on the ideas of collaborative discovery and participation is the outcome of these technical breakthroughs (Selwyn, 2012). Mobile devices and social media may be used by students to connect with teachers, friends, and resources, as well as to access course information (Cavus & Ibrahim, 2008, 2009; Richardson & Lenarcic, 2008).

Using social media platforms at academic institutions, students may also interact with their mentors, access their course materials, personalize them, and create student communities (Greenhow, 2011a, 2011b). More than 75% of teenagers utilize social networking sites for online education (DeBell & Chapman, 2006; Lenhart, Arafeh, & Smith, 2008; Lenhart, Madden, & Hitlin, 2005). Ninety percent of school-age youngsters regularly use the internet. According to the findings of a focus group with students from three American universities, social media offered opportunities for group learning and inspired and enticed students to participate in various extracurricular activities (Gikas & Grant, 2013). However, the application and usage of social media and mobile devices is a relatively new phenomenon that has received little research. As a result, it is crucial to note that this incorporation of social media does not only expand its usage for students' amusement; it may also include a considerable

alteration in the conventional roles of educators and students. Regarding educators' function, instructors (and lecturers) are crucial to successfully adopting SNSs as learning environments (Hutchens & Hayes, 2014; Vázquez-Martnez & Cabero-Almenara, 2015).

Empirical Review

Ansari and Khan (2020) investigated a hitherto unstudied area of research: using social media and mobile devices to communicate with professors at higher education institutions across institutional borders and transfer resources. This empirical study aims to comprehend students' perceptions of social media and mobile devices through collaborative learning, interaction with peers and teachers, and their impact on academic performance. It is based on a survey of 360 students from an eastern Indian university. A structural equation model based on latent variance was employed for measurement and instrument validation. The results showed that adopting online social media for collaborative learning significantly affected peer interaction, teacher interaction, and online knowledge-sharing behaviour. Students' engagement has a considerable influence on academic achievement and has been significantly impacted by interaction with professors, classmates, and online knowledge-sharing behaviour. As a result of this finding, it is essential to point out that online social media for group learning inspires students to be more imaginative, dynamic, and research focused.

According to the findings of the eight Egyptian universities, social media significantly affects higher education institutions, notably in terms of teaching and learning resources. Similarly, according to research by Gikas & Grant (2013), social media and electronic devices provide students the chance to learn collaboratively and enable them to share materials with their classmates. However, due to several limitations, academic members seldom use social media (internet accessibility, mobile devices, etc.).

A study conducted by Mabic (2014) of students at the Faculty of Economics at the University of Mortar in Bosnia and Herzegovina found that social media is already used for information sharing and material sharing and that students are prepared to use social networking sites (such as slide share, etc.) for educational purposes, particularly e-learning and communication. This study found that most faculty members used social media for work-related purposes and that the interactive nature of online and mobile technologies helps create a better learning environment for students worldwide. Faculty members also used social media to teach students about international business, share content with students who were far away.

Facebook and YouTube were used by more than half of the 148 higher education institutions, according to Reuben's 2008 study on social media use among professional schools. However, a recent study of 456 accredited US schools discovered that all of them utilize social media in some capacity, with Facebook accounting for 98 percent and Twitter accounting for 84 percent, respectively, of their e-learning and mentor interaction (Barnes & Lescault, 2011). Furthermore, 83 percent of internet users between the ages of 18 and 29 who use social media said they do it to connect with coworkers, according to Madden and Zickuhr (2011).

Theoretical framework: Technology Acceptance Model

The study is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). In 1989, Davis introduced the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Ajzen and Fishbein 1980 adapted the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) from TAM. This theory is believed to be an offshoot of mass media's uses and gratification theory. The primary constructs influencing behavioural intention are Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). Davis believed in 1989 that perceived ease of use refers to the level to which an individual believes that using a particular system would be easy and free of stress. While perceived usefulness relates to the users' behaviour intent to utilize an information system, their perception of the system's utility is mostly what drives this intention (Davis et al., 1989). Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is widely used and accepted to explain the relationship between

perceptions and the use of technology, such as the use of social media for communication between lecturers and students. This is in a way different from using the media in setting the agenda as captioned in Oji (2006).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted an online survey method of scientific inquiry using social media and Google forms. This method was selected for its topic demands to elicit people's opinions on the topic being studied. The population of this study was a WhatsApp group purposively created for this study. The group comprised 265 members – 263 lecturers and students and two researchers.

Given the size of the population, the researcher adopted the census sampling principle. The principle states that when the population is small, the researchers should sample all the elements of the population. So, the sample size for this study remained at 263. The availability sampling technique was adopted for this study. According to Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2012), convenience sampling (also known as availability sampling) is a non-probability sampling method that uses data collected from population members who are conveniently available to participate in the study. To ascertain respondents' availability, date, and time as stipulated on the group for filling in the online questionnaire.

Only respondents available on the stipulated date and time were sampled for the study. The researchers used an online questionnaire for this study. The Google survey was used to create an eighteen-item questionnaire for the study. Two hundred sixty-three respondents filled in and submitted the online questionnaire created on Google form. A link to the form was made available on the WhatsApp group for respondents to access on the stipulated date and time. The researchers gave a space of three days to ensure that forms were appropriately filled. The researchers used frequency tables and pie charts to present data generated from the study. The percentage was used to analyze the presented data.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Demographic Data

The researchers assessed the demographic variables of the respondents to ensure that they represented the population of the study. Since the researcher used an online survey, it was necessary to first and foremost establish the tertiary affiliation of the respondents:

Figure 1: University Affiliation (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 1 implies that a majority of the respondents for this study were from Imo State University. Also, the following top-ranking schools whose students and lecturers share an opinion in this study are Delta State Polytechnic, Delta State University, and the University of Lagos.

Figure 2: Academic Strata of Respondents (Researcher, 2022).

The researcher used this figure to establish the extent to which the data for this study represented the two parties involved in the communication experience under study. The study, using Figure 2, reveals that both parties took part in the study, but the majority of the respondents for the study were students. Thus, this study would most appropriately be generalized in favour of the students. Most of the opinions (85%) shared in this study represent students' opinions.

Figure 3: Gender Distribution of the Respondents (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 3 implies that this study captures the opinion of both male and female lecturers and students. However, it shows that the sampled respondents had a gender gap of 12% in favour of females. Thus, the participants of the study were mostly female.

Figure 4: Educational Qualification (Researcher, 2022).

The researcher uses this figure to establish the extent of knowledge of the respondents on the subject matter under study. The figure shows that most respondents (48%) were masters or postgraduate students in their respective universities. This shows that most of the respondents have constantly interacted with lecturers throughout their bachelor's degrees and have had encounters with supervisors too. Also, this figure shows a representation of four educational levels among the respondents of the study.

Psychographic Data

This data group is collected, analyzed, and presented to answer research questions to establish research objectives. The following are the research questions raised in this study: To what extent are social media used for lecturers-student communication at Delta State Polytechnic? Which social media platform is mainly used for lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic? How do students and lecturers perceive using social media for lecturer-student communication at Delta State Polytechnic? Furthermore, in what ways has the use of social media affected lecturer-student communication at Delta State Polytechnic?

Research Question 1: To what extent are social media is used for lecturers-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic?

Figures 5, 6, and 7 provide answers to research question 1. These figures show the use of social media, Frequency of Communication with Lecturers or Students using social media, and Extent of Communication with Students or Lecturers using social media.

Figure 5: Use of social media (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 5 showed that some of the study's respondents did not use social media to interact with their lecturers. They had other platforms through which they engaged in lecturers-students communication. Initially, the researcher intended to consider the response from this 13% invalid. Nevertheless, their option was retained because they are students and lecturers will still have adequate knowledge about the subject matter under study.

Also, their opinion in the following figure will show other media platforms that can be used for interactions among lecturers and students.

Figure 6: Frequency of Communication with Lecturers or Students using Social Media (Researcher, 2022).

As some respondents said they rarely or never use these platforms, a quick look at the figure above will reveal. Figure 6 shows that students and lecturers (over 25%) usually engage in social media interactions. The combination of those utilizing media is much more than the percentage of respondents who did not use these platforms.

Figure 7: Extent of Communication with Students or Lecturers using Social Media (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 7 shows a great extent of social media use for lecturer-students communication in selected universities in Nigeria. This shows that students and lecturers use social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, and Twitter to interact and relate. If this is the case, examining which social media platform was mainly used is necessary. The following figure captures this.

Research Question 2: Which social media platform is mostly use for lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic?

Figures 8 and 9 answer this research question. These figures show that social media platforms are mainly used to communicate with students or lecturers and the reasons for the choice of social media platforms.

Figure 8: Social Media Platform mostly used to Communicate with Students or Lecturers (Researcher, 2022). From figure 8, WhatsApp ranks as the most used social media platform for lecturers-students communication, as opined by over 70% of the respondents. Some respondents opined that they used Microsoft Teams, Telegram, and Google Meet to interact with lecturers or students. Facebook and Twitter are barely or never used for this type of interaction. The reason for this high rate of the use of WhatsApp is seen in the following figure.

Figure 9: Reasons for the Choice of Social Media Platform. (Researcher, 2022). Figure 9 shows that ease of use and perceived usefulness are why respondents tend to communicate with lecturers and students using social media. This can also be deduced why WhatsApp is the most used social media platform for communication between lecturers and students. This social media platform, especially during project supervision, can make communication between supervisor and supervisee easy and smooth. However, the following figure shows how students and lecturers react to social media for project supervision communication.

Research Question 3: How do students and lecturers perceive the use of social media for lecturerstudent communication in Delta State Polytechnic?

Figures 10 to 15 provide answers to this research question. From figure 10 (below), although social media is an easy and convenient means of lecturers' and students' communication, project supervisors are perceived by students and lecturers to find using these platforms for communication during project supervision unofficial. While some supervisors do not have any issue communicating with their supervisees via any medium possible, others are adamant about accepting this trend used mainly for distant learning. This accounts for one of the cases affecting supervisors' flexibility.

Figure 10: Project Supervisors find it Unofficial to Communicate with Supervisees. (Researcher, 2022).

Also, it is anticipated that social media's ease of use makes lecturers physically distanced from students. This is shown in the following figure.

Figure 11: Ease of Use of Social Media makes Lecturer Physical distanced from Students (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 11 shows that a majority of the respondents agree with the claim that ease of use of social media makes lecturers physical distanced from students. This can be most applicable in terms of project supervisor. Take, for instance, if a supervisor allows his or her candidate to interact with them via social media platforms, there will be little or no need for the supervisee to be physically present except in very critical circumstances. This has its advantages and disadvantages as well.

Figure 12: Use of Social Media Platform makes it easier to Communicate with Lecturers. (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 12 shows that most of the respondents (48%) strongly agree that using social media platforms makes it easier to communicate with lecturers. Although none disagreed, a handful of the respondents strongly opposed this assertion. The majority supported the claim. This implies that the use of social media for lecturers-students communication was perceived as being easy to use and valuable.

(Researcher, 2022).

Figure 13: The Use of Social Media Platforms makes Communication with Lecturers Timely

Figure 13 shows that many respondents believe using social media platforms makes communication with lecturers timely.

Figure 14: Social Media Use for Communication creates Avenue for more contact with Lecturers when a student needs Guidance (Researcher, 2022).

Also, Figure 14 below reveals that a large percent of the respondents agreed that using social media for lecturers-students communication has significant tendencies to create an avenue for more frequent contact with lecturers and students when a student needs guidance.

Figure 15: Lecturers are Open to Conversation only from Course Representatives (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 15, it was disagreed by a majority of the respondents (49%) that lecturers are open to conversation only from course representatives. This implies that students perceived those lecturers are open to a conversation from any one of the students.

Figure 16: Availability of Lecturers for Social Media Communication with Students (Researcher, 2022).

From figure 16, it is revealed that only a few lecturers are readily available to interact with students via social media. This implies that the respondents of this study believe that most lecturers are not always available to interact with students via social media platforms.

Research Question 4: In what ways does the use of social media has affected lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic?

Figures 17 to 20 provide findings that collectively answer the research question..

Figure 17: Use of social media for Lecturer-Student Communication fosters Mentor/Mentee Interaction (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 17 shows that most respondents (52%) use social media to foster mentor/mentee interaction for lecturer-student communication. By implication, in as much as only a few lecturers use social media for interactions with students, this interaction fosters relationships between lecturers who serve as mentors and students who serve as mentees.

Figure 18: Social Media Use for Lecturer-Student Communication makes Lecturers accessible to the student

Figure 18: Social Media Use for Lecturer-Student Communication makes Lecturers accessible by Student (Researcher, 2022).

Still, on the effects of social media on lecturer-students communication, figure 18 shows a high level of accessibility between lecturers and students who interact using social media. A majority of the respondents strongly agreed with this assertion.

Figure 19: Use of social media for Lecturer-Student Communication opens Room for Familiarity which leads to Contempt. (Researcher, 2022).

Figure 19 revealed that using social media for lecturer-student communication opens room for familiarity, which leads to contempt, as opined by most respondents (38%).

Figure 20: Ease of Use of Social Media makes Lecturer Physically Distanced from Students (Researcher, 2022). Figure 20 shows that a majority of the respondents (41%) agree that the ease of use of social media in communication makes lecturers physically distanced from students. That is, lecturers who primarily interact with their students using social media tend to rely more on the ease of use of these platforms and might be tempted to skip physical appearances.

Test of Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the execution of this study:

Hypothesis 1: Social media platforms are not significantly used for lecturers-student communication in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Recall Table for Figure 7

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Very high extent	26	11%
High extent	104	44%
Low extent	78	33%
Very low extent	26	11%
Total	234	100%

(Researcher, 2022)

Table 1: Chi-square Test for Hypothesis 1

Response	Observed	Expected	O _i - E _i	(O _i -E _i) ² (O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
Very high extent	26	58.5	-32.5	1056.25	18.05555556
High extent	104	58.5	45.5	2070.25	35.38888889
Low extent	78	58.5	19.5	380.25	6.5
Very low extent	26	58.5	-32.5	1056.25	18.05555556
Total	234				

Calculated Chi Square 78

Degree of Freedom 2
Alpha Level 0.05
Critical Chi Square Value 5.99

(Researcher, 2022)

From table 1, it is shown that the calculated chi-square value is greater than the critical (or tabulated) chi-square value. Therefore, the null hypothesis that social media is not significantly used for lecturers-students communication is rejected. Thus, the alternative statement is accepted, statistically establishing that social media is believed by students and lectures sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions to be significantly used for lecturers-students communication.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between social media usage and lecturerstudent communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Recall Table for Figure 9

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	113	48%
Agree	69	29%
Neutral	35	15%
Disagree	0	0%
Strongly Disagree	17	7%
Total	234	100%

(Researcher, 2022)

Table 2: Chi Square Test for Hypothesis 2

Response	Observed	Expected	Oi - Ei	(Oi-Ei) ²	(Oi-Ei) ² /Ei	
Strongly Agree	113	58.5	54.5	2970.25	50.77350427	
Agree	69	58.5	10.5	110.25	1.884615385	
Neutral	35	58.5	-23.5	552.25	9.44017094	
Disagree		0	58.5	-58.5	3422.25	58.5
Strongly Disagree		17	58.5	-41.5	1722.25	29.44017094
Total		234				

Calculated Chi Square 150.0384615

Degree of Freedom 2
Alpha Level 0.05
Critical Chi Square Value 5.99

(Researcher, 2022)

Table 2 shows that the calculated chi-square value (150.0385) is greater than the critical (or tabulated) chi-square value (5.99). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected: social media is not significantly easy to use and valuable for lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions. Thus, the alternative statement is accepted, statistically establishing that students and lecturers believe that social media is not significantly easy to use and valuable for lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Hypothesis 3: Social media usage has no significant effect on lecturer-student communication at Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Recall Table for Figure 17

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	0	0%
Agree	86	37%
Neutral	35	15%
Disagree	69	29%
Strongly Disagree	43	18%
Total	234	100%

(Researcher, 2022)

Table 3: Chi Square Test for Hypothesis 3

Response	Observed	Expected	Oi - Ei	(Oi-Ei)^2	(Oi-Ei)^2/Ei	
Strongly Agree	0	58.5	-58.5	3422.25	58.5	
Agree 86	58.5	27.5	756.25	12.92735043		
Neutral35	58.5	-23.5	552.25	9.44017094		
Disagree		69	58.5	10.5	110.25	1.884615385
Strongly Disagree		43	58.5	-15.5	240.25	4.106837607
Total		234				
Calculated Chi Square		86.85897436				
Degree of Freedom		2				
Alpha Level		0.05				
Critical Chi Square Value		5.99				

(Researcher, 2022)

From table 3, it is shown that the calculated chi-square value (86.8589) is greater than the critical (or tabulated) chi-square value (5.99). Therefore, the null hypothesis that social media is not significantly easy to use and valuable for lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic is rejected. Thus, the alternative statement is accepted, statistically establishing that students and lecturers believe that the use of social media significantly affects lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions in a negative way.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

WhatsApp ranking the highest of the most used social media platform for lecturer-students interaction; social media is believed by students and lecturers sampled in these Nigerian tertiary institutions to be significantly used for lecturer-students communication. Despite the spread of social media among the respondent sampled, communication between lecturers and students is one-sided, as lecturers only accept messages from the course representative. It was further discovered that even though social media is agreed to have been an excellent source for communication in a post-covid19 era. Transitioning into this media fully for lecturer-student communication in the sampled Nigerian tertiary institution posed some difficulty. Results from hypothesis three establish that students and lecturers believe that the use of social media significantly affects lecturer-student communication in sampled Nigerian tertiary institutions in a negative way. Lecturers believed that an open room for student access and communication breeds insults, over-familiarity, and a lack of respect in real life.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the effect of social media on the student-lecturer relationship has significantly been explored. Greenhow (2011) confidently noted that through social media, students are granted access to communicate with their mentors and course materials and develop student communities. In the cause of this study, several works of different scholars were examined. The objective was to determine the extent to which social media is used for lecturers-student communication at Delta State Polytechnic. Ascertain the social media platform mainly used for lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic; examine how students and lecturers perceive the use of social media for lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic and determine various ways in which the use of social media has affected lecturer-student communication in Delta State Polytechnic.

Based on the given objective, significant findings from the study revealed that most students and lecturers use social media for their various personal communications. It was further discovered that less than 25% of respondents use social media for student-lecturer interaction. Results further tested showed that transitioning into this media fully for lecturer-student communication in the sampled Nigerian tertiary institution posed some form of difficulty as Lecturers believed an open room for student access to everyday interaction would breed insults and lack of respect in the long run. The following recommendations were arrived at;

1. Adaptability to social media space/platforms and its flexibility in communication should be encouraged.
2. Lecturers should set boundaries limiting students to an interaction that promotes academic discussion.
3. Lecturers should intentionally create a room that fosters a mentor-mentee relationship by engaging the students through social media discussions.

References

- Alexander, P. (2022). Shared discursive history, rethinking teachers as role models. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 30(4), 529-547.
- Ansari, A. N. J. & Khan, N. A. (2020). *Exploring the role of social media in collaborative learning the new domain of learning*. Smart Learning Environments, 7 (9), 1 – 16.
- Barnes, N. G., & Lescault, A. M. (2011). *Social media adoption soars as higher-ed experiments and reevaluates its use of new communications tools*. North Dartmouth: Center for Marketing Research. University of Massachusetts Dartmouth.
- Cavus, N., & Ibrahim, D. (2008). *A mobile tool for learning English words*. Online Submission, 6 – 9.
- Cavus, N., & Ibrahim, D. (2009). *M-learning: An experiment in using SMS to support learning new English language words*.
- DeBell, M., & Chapman, C. (2006). *Computer and internet use by students in 2003*. Statistical analysis report. NCES 2006-065. National Center for education statistics. Educause Center for Applied Research [ECAR] (2012)
- Gikas, J., & Grant, M. M. (2013). *Mobile computing devices in higher education: Student perspectives on learning with cellphones, smartphones & social media*. Internet and Higher Education Mobile, 19, 18–26.

- Greenhow, C. (2011a). *Online social networks and learning*. *On the horizon*, 19(1), 4–12.
- Greenhow, C. (2011b). *Youth, learning, and social media*. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 45(2), 139–146
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! *The challenges and opportunities of social media*. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68.
- Lenhart, A., Arafeh, S., & Smith, A. (2008). *Writing, technology and teens*. Pew Internet & American Life Project.
- Lenhart, A., Madden, M., & Hitlin, P. (2005). *Teens and technology* (p. 2008). Washington, DC: Pew Charitable Trusts Retrieved September 29.
- Madden, M., & Zickuhr, K. (2011). *65% of online adults use social networking sites*. Pew Internet & American Life Project, 1, 14.
- Nihalani, P. K., & Mayrath, M. C. (2010). Statistics I. *Findings from using an iPhone app in a higher education course*. In White Paper.
- Oji, M., & Bebenimibo, P. (2021). An Examination of Social Media Reportage and Its Impact Towards Promoting School Development in Nigeria: A Study of Success Adegor's Viral Video.
- Oji, M. (2011). Awareness of interpersonal and mediated poverty alleviation communications in the Niger Delta.
- Oji, M. (2006). Communication and conflict resolution: The peace media initiative.
- Okoye, I. E. (2004). Needs Gratification Versus Knowledge Gaps: A comparative Study of the Uses of Satellite and Local Television”.
- Reuben, B. R. (2008). *The use of social media in Higher Education for marketing and communications: A guide for professionals in higher education* (Vol. 5)
- Richardson, J., & Lenarcic, J. (2008). *Text Messaging as a Catalyst for Mobile Student Administration:*
- Rimm-Kaufman, S. (2015, March 9). Improving students' relationships with teachers. American Psychological Association.
- Schonert-Reichl, K. A. (2017). Social and emotional learning and teachers. *The future of children*, 137-155.
- Selwyn, N. (2012). *Making sense of young people, education and digital technology: The role of sociological theory*. *Oxford Review of Education*, 38(1), 81–96.
- Zhu, C. (2012). *Student satisfaction, performance, and knowledge construction in online collaborative learning*.